

IMPORTANCE OF TACHING AND LEARNING MATERIALS IN PRE-SCHOOLS

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Abstract: This article is intended to investigate the influence of teaching and learning materials on children performance in pre-schools

Key words: teaching and learning materials, pre-schools, young children, self-confidence, self-discipline

INTRODUCTION.

The preschool years are very important in life of an individual. The foundation for learning and for basic attitudes is laid during the five years of life. To stimulate learning and foster healthy growth and development, children should be provided with appropriate materials and care. During pre - school years, basic skills such as jumping, climbing, dancing and hopping can be developed. Because children construct knowledge actively interacting with the physical environment in developmental stages. They learn through their own individual actions and exploration. Teaching kindergarten kids should be carried out in the atmosphere of consistent active games as “one of the valuable tools to create learning atmosphere where children learn while are being engaged in interaction and cooperation. Kindergarten curriculum follows the curriculum approved by the Ministry of Education which gives a clear guidance for learning and teaching. Moreover, the kindergarten has flexibility in determining how delivery of the curriculum can best take place.

Teaching and learning materials are vital to any successful teaching and learning process worldwide. This is because these resources aid the teacher to effectively transfer the content to the preschool learner. Moreover, they are used for teaching

young children to understand what they are being taught. Provision of teaching and learning resources make the bone of the environment in that children are able to relate what is in the environment and what they are being taught in classroom. Children learn better with real direct first-hand experience. Children in pre - schools learn through their senses of hearing, tasting, feeling, seeing and touching. For them to learn well they should be provided with a variety of instructional materials. In pre - school teaching and learning resources play an important role in instilling knowledge, skills and values to the learners. Availability of teaching and learning materials and effective use reflects on quality of teaching of the subject. This is because most of the resources play an important role in understanding of concepts and importing skills to the learner. Use of resources in pre-schools is vital, it promotes experiential learning. Literate parents are aware of the impact of resources and their usage. Parents looking for a school to enroll their children consider the availability of both indoor and outdoor resources.

Attention is drawn to the fact that children learn through activities which are the highest phrase for children's development. Through activities, they are able to discover, explore and achieve optimum learning. Early childhood learning is through getting involved in manipulating objects (by doing) which nourishes every aspect of children's development that forms the foundation of intellectual social and emotional skills necessary for school and in life. Appropriate materials provide new experience for children and motivate them to learn from one another. Children at 3-5 years learn best through concrete materials which are manipulated through sorting and grouping. These materials enable them to develop of their senses at preschool. The use of teaching learning materials gives more direct emphasis, rewards and reinforces in the teaching process. Teachers who vary children's learning through action and interaction with others and the environment with a variety of materials, or aids, makes the class room look colorful and portray the relevance and themes in each lesson for children. The usage of instructional materials also makes the teaching easier, hence understanding and retention on the part of learners. Therefore, the use

of teaching / learning materials may affect performance either positively or negatively.

With the help of teaching and learning materials children understand abstract concept, solve problems and develop critical thought process, for example they teach the concept of number (building blocks). Instructional materials also encourage collaboration in solving problems by having children work in groups to discuss and solve problems together. Children also are able to interact with others, adapt new technology and think through logically.

Moreover, teachers can help learners to control their emotions as they interact with teaching and learning materials. For example, problems such as aggression shyness, thumb sucking, bullying fighting and temper are associated at early stage and through the teachers and parents they are able to help solve the problem as early as possible. Pre-school improve the physical health and abilities of the child through the emotional and social development. The child is encouraged by his or her self-confidence, curiosity and self-discipline. Pre - School are important in that they establish patterns and expectations of success which help to create a climate of confidence for the child's future learning effort.

Teachers should-understand the objectives of play materials to the children which are to explore, and develop personal talents and skills. Play materials increase children's vocabulary and self-expression as children play freely, their large and small motor skills develop, body muscles are strengthened, control and coordinate various parts of the body, develop their accuracy estimation of skills, relax and enjoy themselves. Therefore, it is very essential for pre - school educators to provide young children with a variety of play materials.

Teaching and learning materials stimulate the total growth and development of children. The materials are used to cater for the following areas, manipulating skills, visual perception, motor skills, auditory perception, language development, exploration through feeling and social emotional needs. They should be adequate for all the children / learners to interact with them. By interacting with their peers, children learn much about the world. They can learn much better if they are provided

with teaching / learning materials. This builds their self-confidence, self-esteem and master contain skills.

In spite of the fact that teaching and learning resources are encouraged so as to enable the learners retain what they have been taught, still the learners have difficulties in retaining what they have been taught. Children develop their imaginative, discovery and creative skills through the use of teaching/ learning materials, learners are able to explore familiarize and eventually understand unfamiliar objects when they interact with them. Instructional resources provide children with a means of expressive feelings, concerns, and interests as well as acting as a channel for social interactions with adults and other children. Through the use of instructional materials learners are able to explore, familiarize and eventually understand unfamiliar objects when they interact with them.

Play materials are part of teaching and learning materials. Play is an important vehicle of learning among children. Although the children spontaneously device play, an attentive teacher needs to support and nourish it by providing play materials to children. Children as they play can gain important insights, in what children are thinking and feeling. Play gives a child a chance to develop the qualities of endurance, tolerance, sympathy, self-control, the art of giving and receive

Creative play is an important means of encouraging children to experiment and explore the world around. It helps to discover through the learners' senses and properties of different materials. If provided with a wide range of activities they can develop, physical, social, emotional and intellectual skills. When activities are led in a positive way children can gain a great deal of satisfaction from creative play and increase their confidence.

Young learners can be given any type of object that will be safe for them to touch and hold. Some of these materials are for example wood, shell, fruits and natural sponges. These objects promote children's development which thus promotes a different range of hand movement. Therefore, it is good to provide learners various teaching materials. Furthermore, the usage of these resources in learning process arouse interest that create a desire to learn, stimulate the pupils' imagination, give a

concrete impression of the concept and promote retention of ideas. They as well help consolidate what has been learned, illustrate relationships, making learning more real and develop in learner manipulative skills.

CONCLUSION.

Quality early childhood education is very vital in every society, and Uzbek society is not an exception. Curriculum, materials, teaching methods and evaluation should all be designed for learners and their needs. These materials are part of the process. They help children to develop imaginative, discovery and creative skills through familiarization with the materials as they interact with them. It is important therefore to state that the use of teaching and learning materials makes it possible for children to grasp concepts and skills very fast if well utilized.

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